

GA-based approach to optimize an equivalent electric circuit model of a Li-ion battery-pack

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Abstract

This article presents the optimization procedure based on genetics algorithms (GA) to obtain an equivalent electric circuit model (EECM) of a Li-ion battery pack. In the first part, a series of experimental tests in time and frequency domains were carried out. These tests were used to identify the parameters of the EECM under different State-of-Charge (SoC) for a commercial battery-pack. Each EECM consists of a voltage source connected in series with a resistor and a set of k networks composed of a resistor in parallel with a capacitor, where $k = 1, 2$ or 3 (1RC, 2RC, and 3RC). Subsequently, parametric identification of the EECM was performed using optimization techniques. At this stage, the topology that gives the lowest estimation error was determined, where the options analyzed were to use 1RC, 2RC, or 3RC. The objective function consists of minimizing the mean square error between measured and calculated impedances of the different proposed circuit models. Genetic Algorithm (GA) was used to solve this optimization problem. The minimum error obtained was 1.07% and 1.05% for the EECM with 2RC and 3RC networks, respectively. Finally, these EECMs were implemented in Matlab®/Simulink to validate the Li-ion battery-pack model response for an electric vehicle application experimentally. A hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) simulation platform was developed to simulate the performance of an electric vehicle (EV) under different driving cycles. The results show that the GA-based approach allows obtained an EECM of low order to represent the highly dynamic behavior of a Li-ion battery with high accuracy.

Keywords: Li-ion battery-pack, Equivalent Electric Circuit, Genetic Algorithm, Electric Vehicle applications, HIL simulation.

1. Introduction

Li-ion batteries are critical components in the development of electric vehicles (EVs). A series and parallel combination of several Li-ion cells are connected to obtain the nominal voltage and capacity for battery-packs used in EVs (Haifeng et al., 2009; Jaguemont et al., 2016; J. Li & Mazzola, 2013). Although the cells have the same manufacturing process, there are slight differences among them that can affect the operating conditions of the battery pack. In general, battery packs of an EV operate in a range of 90% and 20% of the state-of-charge (SoC). Therefore, batteries require a battery management system (BMS) to monitoring their

states, to ensure their voltage and current limits, to control charging/discharging processes and for temperature and cell-balancing control (Cheng et al., 2011). To perform all these tasks, the BMS needs a high accuracy battery model to predict its behavior. Models vary according to their complexity. For example, the electrochemical models are very accurate, but these are not easy to parameterize, and simulations require high computational capacity (Saidani et al., 2017).

The equivalent electric circuit model (EECM) has been very used in the literature because it has high accuracy and simplicity to represent the electrochemical processes that occur inside a Li-ion battery (Andre et al., 2011; Pizarro-Carmona et al., 2019). Different EECMs have been developed to model different type of battery behavior, for example, a simple EECM that consist of a dependent voltage source with a series resistance is a useful model to represent the stationary regime of the battery. However, in many applications such as EV, it is necessary to have a model that can adequately describe the dynamic response of the battery. Therefore, to improve accuracy, other components should be added to the model, such as capacitors, parallel resistance-capacitor (RC) combinations, inductance, and constant phase element (CPE). This last component has been widely used in recent battery model research. The CPE is a fractional element that produces a partially resistive and capacitive behavior; therefore, it contributes to the circuit with a phase between 0° to 90° (J. Xu et al., 2013). The differential equation that represents a CPE is fractional, and its numerical solution requires infinite power series, which produces inaccurate solutions with high time processing (Podlubny, 1999). However, it is possible to reproduce the effect of a CPE utilizing multiple RC networks in series. The decision on the order of the RC network depends on the required accuracy and the available computational capacity (Hu et al., 2009). In order to improve the accuracy in EECM with low-order RC components, many studies have employed intelligent algorithms to optimize the Li-ion battery model, such as the unscented Kalman filter (Baba et al., 2016; Tian et al., 2014). Bayesian Networks have also been used to obtain a low-order EECM, achieving high precision when using a circuit with 2RC and 3RC components compared to the fitting upon deterministic least-square regression of a commercial impedance analyzer (K. Khan et al., 2018).

The parameters of an electric circuit can be determined through time and frequency domain tests. The time-domain test is used to determine the relationship between the open-circuit voltage and SoC. In this test, a series of charge/discharge current pulses are applied to the battery during a complete cycle. When the battery is charged/discharged and subsequently the current is interrupted, the battery reaches the maximum voltage, a condition that is known as open-circuit voltage (OCV). In this way, the analysis of voltage and current in terminals allows determining the OCV-SoC relationship (Dubarry & Liaw, 2007; He et al., 2012; Jiménez-Bermejo et al., 2018). Also, this test can be used to obtain the parameters of the EECM from the battery voltage response. However, the impedance determined in the domain time is only valid for constant current, and it is difficult to achieve an exact model because the precise determination of some singular points on the terminal voltage is a difficult task (Castano-Solis et al., 2019).

Additionally, to this time test, domain frequency tests can be performed to improve battery model accuracy. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is the most used technique to analyze electrochemical storage systems, such as Li-ion batteries. In this technique, a small AC excitation voltage-signal is applied to the battery in a given frequency range (from about milli-Hertz to Mega-Hertz). The current and voltage are measured at each frequency, and the complex impedance is calculated as the ratio of the current and voltage complex (Hammouche et al., 2004; Wu et al., 2014). In this way, a Nyquist graph is generated where the x-axis represents the real part of the impedance, while on the y-axis, the negative of the imaginary part of the impedance is represented. The correct interpretations of this graph allow determining the parameters of an EECM for the Li-ion battery (R. Li et al., 2010; Pattipati et al., 2011).

Different techniques have been used to model a battery-pack in the literature, which can be classified into three main methods. The first one consists of representing the complete battery-pack adding serial and parallel cell circuits. The main drawback of this model is that it does not consider the variations between cells and the

thermal imbalance of the battery, among others (Dubarry et al., 2009; Sen & Kar, 2009). The second technique is to scale the cell model to a battery-pack model. This model has the advantage of being faster in simulations compared to the first technique, but not consider the variations between cells and the thermal imbalance of the battery (Kim et al., 2011; Xiong et al., 2013). The third methodology consists of directly constructing a battery-pack model that can represent the complete behavior of the pack. This type of model produces better results since it naturally considers the characteristics of the cell and its thermal influences (Castano-Solis, Gauchia, et al., 2017; Ko et al., 2019; Ye et al., 2019).

This paper presents a Genetic Algorithm (GA) based approach to identifying parameters of an EECM associated with different frequencies, and that represents the electrical behavior of a lithium-ion battery pack. To consider the variations between cells, packaging, and control system effects on the battery-pack behavior, the experimental tests are performed directly to a commercial battery pack. These tests are performed in both time and frequency domains to obtain the OCV-SoC relation and the complex impedance at different SoC, respectively. Through the frequency domain test, different EECMs were obtained, which included an SoC dependent voltage source, one resistance and 1RC, 2RC, and 3RC networks. The parameters of the EECMs are obtained by formulating an optimization problem whose objective function minimizes the mean square error between the measured and estimated impedance of the different circuit models proposed. This optimization problem is solving using GA. Each EECM is experimentally validated using a hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) platform that reproduces real driving conditions of an EV.

The contents of this paper are organized as follows: Section 2 presents the experimental configuration for time and frequency domain tests. Next, Section 3 describes the battery-pack modeling represented by an EECM with different orders and also describes the GA-based approach to identifying parameters of the EECM. In Section 4, the EECM with 2RC and 3RC is experimentally validated by means of a HIL simulation of an EV. Finally, Section 5 presents the conclusions of this research.

2. Battery-pack experimental testing

Fig. 1 show the battery pack, which is composed of four parallel strings where each string consists of a "series control board." Each string consists of seven cells connected in series. The pack also includes a BMS that controls the cell voltage, temperature, and current at each serial connection. In addition, it has cell balance functions, protection functions for over-charging and over-discharging, monitoring the SoC, and state-of-health (SoH) of the battery pack.

Fig. 1. Schematic battery-pack layout.

For the battery pack shown in Fig. 1, a series of experimental tests to analyze the dynamic behavior are performed. In this way, the response in both time and frequency domain are tested by means of application of charge/discharge current pulses during a complete cycle, and EIS tests for frequency ranges, respectively.

2.1 Time domain tests

The OCV-SoC characteristics represent an ideal voltage source that models the active behavior of the battery pack (Rahimi-Eichi et al., 2013; Xia et al., 2014). Experimental tests are conducted to determine the OCV-SoC characteristics where values of voltages and currents are recorded in the time domain. These laboratory tests consist of applying a series of current pulses to charge or discharge the battery for a complete range of SoC. The main battery pack characteristics are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Battery-pack characteristics.

Cell reference	MP176065int
Pack rated voltage	26.9 V
Pack maximum voltage	29.4 V (4.2 V/cell)
Pack minimum cut-off voltage	20.3 V (2.9 V/cell)
Pack capacity	50 Ah
Pack maximum current	50 A
Range of temperature (charge)	-20 °C to 60 °C
Range of temperature (discharge)	-30 °C to 55 °C

The experimental test begins with the battery pack fully charged, i.e., with a 100% SoC, in this case, when the battery pack voltage reaches 29.4 V (pack maximum voltage). Next, the battery is discharged with pulses of 10 A (constant current) for 30 minutes, followed by 90 minutes of relaxation time. In the relaxation period, the battery voltage increases until it reaches stability; this voltage is called OCV. When the battery is completely discharged, the process is reversed, and it is recharged, applying current pulses of 10 A (current constant) for 30 minutes each, followed by 90 minutes of relaxation time. The upper voltage level in the charging process is imposed at 29.4 V. Results of the OCV in discharge and charge tests do not have a representative deviation because Li-ion cells have low hysteresis.

For this reason, average values have been used to calculate the OCV-SoC relationship. Table 2 shows the average values of OCV obtained experimentally. In Fig. 2 is shown the experimental average OCV, and the OCV fitted by means of a two-order polynomial whose mathematical model is shown in (1).

$$OCV(SoC) = 2.8920 \cdot SoC^2 + 0.5061 \cdot SoC + 26.0283 \quad (1)$$

Table 2. OCV-SoC characteristics.

OCV average	SoC (%)
29.40 V	100
27.94 V	71.5
26.99 V	61.9
26.71 V	52.3
26.53 V	33.1
26.34 V	23.5

Fig. 2. Comparison of experimental and estimated OCV-SoC characteristics.

2.2 Frequency domain tests

The EIS is a technique on frequency domain that allows determining the impedance parameters of an electrochemical system in a frequency range. The fundamental approach of the EIS is to apply a small amplitude sinusoidal excitation signal to the system under analysis and measure the response. Usually, voltage is the excitation signal for a particular frequency, and the response is a current with the same frequency as the applied voltage but different in magnitude and phase. If the amplitude of the voltage applied is small, then the current can be considered linear in a first approximation, where the higher-order terms in the Taylor series expansion for the current can be assumed to be negligible (Ferg et al., 2013; Rodrigues et al., 2000). Therefore, the impedance of the system is calculated as the ratio between voltage and current. The impedance is a complex number usually represented by a magnitude and an angle and depends on frequency applied. One technique that allows a meaningful interpretation of the data is the Nyquist diagram. This diagram is obtained plotting of the real part of impedance against the negative imaginary part for different frequencies. The advantage of Nyquist representation is that it provides a quick overview of the data, and we can make some qualitative interpretations, allowing associating equivalent circuit parameters with the Nyquist graph.

The EIS test has been very used to determine the impedance of the Li-ion cells; therefore, there is enough experience that guarantees satisfactory results for modeling battery pack (Pizarro-Carmona et al., 2019). The experiments were performed using a commercial impedance analyzer, which generates an excitation signal, measures the current and internally calculate the complex impedance on each point of the test (frequency). Commercial analyzers have a significant drawback: they generate considerably low current (100 mA); therefore, to test Li-ion battery pack, it is required to provide higher current signals. In this work, the typical EIS test has been modified accordingly. The frequency sweep signal generated by a commercial impedance analyzer is amplified using the experimental structure proposed in (Castano-Solis, Serrano-Jimenez, et al., 2017). Thus, the impedance of the battery pack is measured for a frequency range from 1 mHz to 5 kHz for five different SoCs (20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, and 90%). Fig. 3 shows the impedance spectrum of the Li-ion battery pack that we are analyzing at five different SoCs. These plots show that variation of SoC affects the impedance of the battery at low and medium frequencies, but above medium frequencies, battery impedance parameters are not affected by changes in SoC.

Different zones can be identified from the impedance spectrum plot of Fig. 3, where each zone is related to different electrochemical processes that occur inside the battery pack, and that can be represented with one or more elements in an EECM. For example, in Fig. 3 the impedance spectrum for an SoC of 90%, low-frequency zone (<4 Hz), is a straight line that can be related to the diffusion process on state solid of Lithium-ion in the electrodes of the battery. This zone is represented in the EECM by a CPE or n-RC components. The medium frequency zones (4 Hz – 316 Hz) form two consecutive semicircles associated with the slow migration of lithium ions through the different solid electrolyte interface (SEI) layers that cover the active mass, and it can be represented in the EECM by 1RC or 2RC components. The high-frequency zone (>316 Hz) is related to an inductive reactance effect attributed to the porosity of the electrodes and the conductors connected between the instrument and the battery. This zone can be represented in an EECM by an inductance. Finally, the intersection with the x-axis is associated with the electrolyte of the cell, and a single resistance represents it in the EECM (Buller et al., 2005; Wang et al., 2015; Y. Xu et al., 2019).

Fig. 3. Impedance spectrum of the Li-ion battery-pack at different SoCs.

3. Battery pack modeling

Estimation of the electrical behavior of the battery pack can be represented by an EECM, as shown in Fig. 4. The EECM has two parts: a voltage-dependent source OCV and an equivalent impedance component, whose parameters are estimated using the experimental data obtained from both time and frequency domain tests performed in section 2, respectively. The impedance component of the EECM consists of a resistor R_0 that models the ohmic resistance of the battery pack, and multiple RC networks in series to represent low and medium frequency impedances. The inductive behavior at the highest frequencies is neglected because the most critical frequency interval for studying the dynamic performance of the battery pack (Castano-Solis, Serrano-Jimenez, et al., 2019) is in the range from 1 mHz to 316 Hz. The goal of this work is to find a low order EECM that allows representing the behavior of the battery pack with high accuracy. In this research, three EECM alternatives were used to describe a battery pack, wherein each option, the 1RC, 2RC, and 3RC networks, were considered. The objective is to analyze the accuracy of each model. Take into consideration the Fig. 4; we can obtain a general expression for the input impedance of the equivalent electrical circuit, which is defined in (2).

$$Z = R_0 + \frac{R_1 \left(\frac{1}{j\omega C_1} \right)}{R_1 + \left(\frac{1}{j\omega C_1} \right)} + \dots + \frac{R_n \left(\frac{1}{j\omega C_n} \right)}{R_n + \left(\frac{1}{j\omega C_n} \right)} \quad (2)$$

The output voltage U_{bat} of the circuit shown in Fig.4 is defined by (3). The inputs of this model are the current i_{bat} in a clockwise direction, the SoC, and the initial value of voltage described in (1). Parameter n is the order of the EECM, u_{C_n} is the voltage in the capacitor n of the RC networks, and the output voltage represents the battery terminal voltage.

$$U_{bat}(SoC, t) = OCV(SoC) - R_0 i_{bat}(t) - u_{C_1}(SoC, t) - \dots - u_{C_n}(SoC, t) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 4. EECM of the battery-pack.

3.1 Genetic Algorithms approach

Genetic Algorithm (GA) is a methodology inspired by nature, which was proposed in 1960 by John Holland, who established its foundation in the book *Adaption in Natural and Artificial Systems* in 1975 (Yau et al., 2012). Specialists have classified GAs as a metaheuristic belonging to a family named Evolutionary Algorithms (EAs), and that is suitable to solve high complexity optimization problems. A problem is highly complex if it is non-convex, discontinue, or combinatorial. An EA is a procedure that emulates a Darwinian evolutionary system, and considers the following step (Chiong et al., 2012):

- a) One population of individuals competing for resources.
- b) One population of individual that is continuously changing due to new births and deaths.
- c) Each individual can survive and reproduce, which depends on its adapt capacity (fitness).
- d) The variations in the reproduction process: offspring are similar to their parent, but not identical.

Then the main idea behind the Darwinian theory is that, on average, species improve their fitness over generations; that is, future generations are better adapted to the environmental conditions.

Let us suppose that we want to maximize a function $f(x)$ subject to $x \in \Omega \subset \mathfrak{R}^n$, where Ω is the space of feasible solutions and n the dimension of vector space. The first step to solve this problem using a GA requires representing each component of the variable x as a gene. Then it is necessary to make a mapping in which the variables of the real problem are coded in a data structure associated with a genetic space, which we will call Ψ . Several alphabets have been used to represent genes, where the most common being the binary set $\{0,1\}$. In a binary set, each component is called a bit. A chromosome is a collection of genes (a string of symbols or bits), and represents a particular characteristic of an individual or solution; L denotes the length of this string. Each chromosome has associated value in the objective function, referred to as fitness. The specific genes are called genotypes, and their representation in the real problem, phenotypes. For example, suppose we have a variable $x = (12,100)$ whose first component represents the voltage of a battery, and the second the capacity in Ah. Let us now assume that gene 001 is associated with the 12 V component, and gene 010 is associated with the 100 Ah capacity. Then, the chromosome that represents this variable in the genetic space is $\psi = 001010$, and it has a phenotype with two attributes; 12-volt and 100-Ah (Simon, 2013).

Once a suitable representation for the chromosome has been defined (L , alphabet, and coding), the next step is to determine the initial population $P(0)$. This process is usually done by randomly selecting chromosomes to form an N -size population. It is also beneficial to use heuristic procedures that incorporate specific knowledge of the problem to be solved.

The third step is to perform evolutionary operations. These operations include selection, crossing, and mutation of individuals. In the selection phase, an $M(k)$ set is constructed with the same number of individuals as $P(k)$. The $M(k)$ set, called the mating pool, can be built using different selection procedures, where the most commonly used are: the roulette-wheel method, tournament, universal stochastic sampling, and elitism (Chong & Zak, 2001). The idea behind these methodologies is to randomly select chromosomes, consider their adaptability, evaluate fitness, avoid bias, and control the selective pressure. High selective pressure leads to a concentration of the search on better-adapted individuals, losing genetic diversity, and producing a premature convergence. Once the mating pool has been built, the crossing operation is performed. In this operation, we chose randomly from the M set two chromosomes (called parents), and a crossing is applied to them, obtaining two new chromosomes (offspring). This operation is made with probability p_c , that is, just $p_c N/2$ chromosomes will be accepted. To carry out the crossing, first, the position of the cross is determined by choosing a random number between 1 and $L-1$. Then, all the bits to the right of the crossing point are swapped, as shown in Fig. 5. The two parents have mated to produce two children, so each child receives genetic information from both parents. Later the parents die, and the children survive to continue the evolutionary process.

Fig. 5. Basic crossover operation.

The final step in the AG is called a mutation. The mutation operation consists of flipping each bit in each chromosome. (1 changes to 0, or 0 changes to 1). These changes are made randomly with mutation probability p_m . The typical values of p_m are in the order of 1%. The value of p_m should be chosen wisely since a considerably high value causes the GA to execute a random search, perform permanent explorations, and lose the exploitation characteristic. On the other hand, a substantially low mutation probability produces inbreeding problems and evolutionary dead ends.

What has been presented up to this point constitutes one generation of the GA. In each generation, the chromosomes that have the best fitness are conserved. The process requires new iterations to achieve solutions that are as close as possible to the global optimum. The most commonly used stopping criterion is to stop the process for a maximum number of iterations (generations) or when the best fitness does not change for several generations. Fig. 6 shows a pseudo-code of a simple genetic algorithm.

```

1.  begin
2.       $k = 0$ 
3.       $P(k) = \text{form\_initial\_population}(N)$ 
4.       $fs(k) = \text{evaluate\_population}(P(k))$ 
5.      while not (termination criteria)
6.           $k = k+1$ 
7.           $M(k) = \text{select\_parent}(P(k-1), fs(k-1))$ 
8.           $P(k) = \text{crossover}(M(k), p_c)$ 
9.           $P(k) = \text{mutation}(P(k), p_m)$ 
10.          $fs(k) = \text{evaluate\_population}(P(k))$ 
11.         [better, worse, avergae] = save_solution_( $P(k), fs(k)$ )
12.     end
13. end

```

Fig. 6. Pseudo-code of a simple genetic algorithm

In this work, GA is used to identify the parameters of the EECM of Fig. 4. GA is usually more robust and allows us to find better quality optimums compared to conventional algorithms. The fitness function chosen is Mean Square Error between the impedance measured in EIS, and EECM impedance defined by (2).

Equation (4) presents the minimization problem that must be solved by the GA.

$$\min \left\{ F(v) = \sum_i \left(Z_i^{\text{med}} - Z_i^{\text{cal}}(v) \right)^2 \right\} \quad (4)$$

where $F(v)$ corresponds at fitness function subject to the constraint $v^{\min} \leq v \leq v^{\max}$. Z_i^{med} is the sample i of the magnitude of the experimentally measured impedance; Z_i^{cal} is the calculated impedance for the sample i provided by the EECM model, and the vector $v = [R_0, R_1, C_1, \dots, R_n, C_n]$ define the design variables.

The implementation of the GA is developed through a script in Matlab®. In this optimization case, the population size is 200. The GA creates three types of children for the next generation, elite, crossover, or mutation. The elite children are individuals in the current generation with the best fitness values. These individuals automatically survive to the next generation. In this work, the following parameters were used: elite population 10, crossover probability p_c , 0.8. and mutation probability p_m , 0.01. After several generations, the fitness function is minimized, and the EECM parameters are obtained. Fig. 7 shows a comparison in the impedance spectrum setting for SoC=90%. The root mean square relative error (RMSE) of the EECM with 1RC, 2RC, and 3RC networks were: 6.26%, 1.07%, and 1.05%, respectively. Therefore, the EECM with 2RC and 3RC components have greater precision to represent the frequency response of the battery pack.

Table 3 and Table 4 show the values of each parameter at different SoC values, for the EECM with 2RC and 3RC components, respectively. It can be seen that R_0 does not have a significant dependency on the SoC; therefore, this element is represented by their average values. The other parameters of both EECM with 2RC and 3RC components are fitted by means of three-order polynomial, which is represented by the general expression given by (5). Table 5 and Table 6 show the coefficients for each parameter of both 2RC and 3RC circuits, respectively. The maximum error of each EECM parameter is less than 4%.

$$\text{parameter}_k(\text{SoC}) = a_1 \text{SoC}^3 + a_2 \text{SoC}^2 + a_3 \text{SoC} + a_4 \quad (5)$$

Fig. 7. Comparison of the experimental and estimated impedance spectrum at 90% SoC.

Table 3. Values of parameters for the EECM with 2RC components.

Element	20% SoC	40% SoC	60% SoC	80% SoC	90% SoC
R0 (Ω)	0.0379	0.0372	0.0374	0.0370	0.0373
C1 (F)	25.014	28.513	10.561	4.418	8.539
R1 (Ω)	0.0276	0.0388	0.0210	0.0154	0.0165
C2 (F)	4183	6839	5336	3441	6450
R2 (Ω)	0.0406	0.0337	0.0176	0.0131	0.0152

Table 4. Values of parameters for the EECM with 3RC components.

Element	20% SoC	40% SoC	60% SoC	80% SoC	90% SoC
R0 (Ω)	0.0358	0.0363	0.0372	0.0371	0.0372
C1 (F)	1.2263	2.2263	0.6627	0.5412	0.5543
R1 (Ω)	0.0096	0.0207	0.0164	0.0042	0.0039
C2 (F)	76.761	62.296	29.802	24.236	22.828
R2 (Ω)	0.0071	0.0136	0.0060	0.0063	0.0062
C3 (F)	4803	3903	2767	5500	6712
R3 (Ω)	0.0276	0.0242	0.0110	0.0155	0.0165

Table 5. Coefficient of parameter equation of the EECM with 2RC component.

Parameter	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4
C1 (F)	526.18	-860.12	381.24	-20.846
R1 (Ω)	0.2949	-0.4367	0.1410	0.0277
C2 (F)	142452	-238068	118155	-11139
R2 (Ω)	0.2905	-0.4288	0.1367	0.0283

Table 6. Coefficient of parameter equation of the EECM with 3RC component.

Parameter	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4
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C1 (F)	45.882	-78.217	37.956	-3.5600
R1 (Ω)	0.2995	-0.5866	0.3278	-0.0351
C2 (F)	438.85	-634.24	170.42	65.111
R2 (Ω)	0.2420	-0.4163	0.2084	-0.0197
C3 (F)	22373	-14858	-3744.2	6039.6
R3 (Ω)	0.2134	-0.2936	0.0887	0.0203

4. Experimental validation

The hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) simulation allows reproducing the electrical requirement of different applications over the battery pack, such as transportation, stationary and portable. In this work, we use a hardware-in-the-loop platform composed of both software and hardware simulation of an EV, as shown in Fig. 8. This HIL platform is deeply explained in (Castano-Solis, Gauchia, et al., 2017). Additionally, Matlab®/Simulink was used to execute simulations of the EV model. The output of the software simulation is used by the dSpace® system to externally control in real-time the power signal of a power source and an electronic load (hardware simulation). Employing this HIL simulation, the behavior of the battery pack under a vehicle application is analyzed. As a result, the voltage response and the current profile of the battery-pack are recorded. Fig. 9 shows a picture of the real HIL platform developed in this research.

Fig. 8. HIL setup diagram.

Fig. 9. HIL experimental platform.

Two different driving cycles are reproducing by the HIL platform. In this work, real-world driving cycles are used instead of lab-based driving cycles to simulate the effects of the environment's conditions and driving style. The driving data was collected from a 2016 Nissan Leaf (Jiménez-Bermejo et al., 2018). A Bluetooth OBDII scanner was installed into the vehicle's OBD port (see Fig. 10), registering data from a CAN-BUS.

The primary data recorded were; SoC, battery pack voltage and current, motor power, auxiliary power, data/time GPS traces measurements.

The driving cycles used present city paths and roadways. The first one, named R1 and shown in Fig. 11, reproduces the extracted current from the battery-pack under a combined route of city and extra-urban paths during 920 s, a maximum speed of 100 km/h, and an average speed of 23 km/h. The second one, named R2 and shown in Fig. 12, reproduces the extracted current from the battery-pack under a mix of city and highway route of 900 s, a maximum speed of 120 km/h, and an average speed above 50 km/h. Fig. 11, and Fig. 12 show the current profiles of R1 and R2, respectively.

Fig. 10. Connection of the sensor in the car.

Fig. 11. R1 current profile.

Fig. 12. R2 current profile.

In section 3, two alternatives of EECM with 2RC and 3RC were obtained to represent the dynamic behavior of the battery pack. The GA-based approach fitted the parameter of both EECMs, and these were represented by a five-order polynomial given by (5) (see Table 4 and Table 5). Equations (5) and the OCV equation given by (1) are included in Matlab®/Simulink, whose input corresponds to the current profiles of the simulated driving cycles. Fig. 13, and Fig. 14 shows the comparison of the measured battery-pack voltage and the simulated battery-pack voltage for each model (with 2RC and 3RC components). Results show that both models with 2RC and 3RC networks present high accuracy to reproduce the dynamic behavior of the battery-pack voltage under real driving conditions.

The RMSE of the voltage responses is 0.30% (2RC) and 0.29% (3RC) for the R1 driving cycle. In the case of the R2 driving cycle, the RMSE is 0.72% (2RC) and 0.58% (3RC). Fig. 14, and Fig. 15 shows the voltage error of both EECM with 2RC and 3RC. The voltage error bound is less than $\pm 2\%$ for these validation tests.

Fig. 13. Simulations results of R1 driving cycle.

Fig. 14. Simulations results of R2 driving cycle.

Fig. 14. Voltage error comparison R1

Fig. 15. Voltage error comparison R2

5. Conclusion

In this work, we optimized three EECMs (1RC, 2RC, and 3RC) for a battery-pack. The parameters of the EECMs were calculated from both time and frequency domain tests. The well-known pulsed current tests are performed to obtain the OCV-SoC relationship, which is represented as a voltage source in the EECMs. Additionally, EIS tests are performed to obtain the complex impedance of the battery pack.

A GA-based approach is used to fitting the parameters of each EECMs utilizing minimizing the fitness function that calculates the mean square error between the measured pack impedance and the simulated pack impedance of each circuit. The comparison of the impedance spectrum from experimental tests and the estimated pack impedance showed that the EECMs with 2RC and 3RC components present the lowest error to represent the frequency response of the battery-pack compared to the EECM with a single RC network. These EECMs are used to describe the behavior of the battery pack.

Both EECMs with 2RC and 3RC networks are experimentally validated using a HIL simulation platform that reproduces two real driving cycles of an electric vehicle when driving urban and highway routes in Madrid. Validation results show that RSME for the R1 driving cycle is 0.30% (2RC) and 0.29% (3RC). In the case of the R2 driving cycle, the RMSE is 0.72% (2RC) and 0.58% (3RC). The maximum error of the voltage response of each EECM is less than 2% for each driving cycle tested.

The main contribution of this research is that it was possible to obtain a low-order EECMs to represent with high accuracy the dynamic behavior of a real battery-pack.

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